

Supplementary Materials

Function *transition* used to determine whether the behaviour sequence follows a non-random pattern using permutations. This method created *nsim* random transitions among behavioural units using the observed sequences, then determined the proportion of random transitions where the values were equal or higher than the value of the observed transition. This proportion represents the probability that the transition observed happened at random. This method gives us an intuitive proxy of non-random transitions without following any specific distribution of errors.

To run the function, you need a table with two columns (*data*): a column with the identity of the individual (or pair) which performed the behaviours and another with the sequence temporarily ordered of the behaviours performed. You also have to define the number of permutations you want (*n.sim*) and if you want to output an observed matrix of transitions by individual (*ind.matrix*).

```
transition=function(data,ind.matrix=FALSE, n.sim=1000)
```

```
{
```

```
#Initial requirements.
```

```
if (class(data)!="data.frame")
```

```
{stop("The object should be a data.frame")}
```

```
if(ncol(data)<2)
```

```
{stop("The object need at least two columns")}
```

```
if (length(data[,1])!=length(data[,2]))
```

```
{stop("The variables have to be the same length")}
```

```
if(sum(is.na(data))!=0)
```

```
{stop("The object should not have NA's ")}
```

```
if(class(data[,1])!="factor"|class(data[,2])!="factor")
```

```
{warning("The variables were transformed to factors")}
```

```
comporta=data
```

```
comporta$ind= as.factor(data[,1])
```

```
comporta$comp= as.factor(data[,2])
```

```
#Creating an empty array to save the observed transitions by pair.
```

```

freq.bruta=array(NA,
dim=c(length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$ind)
)),dimnames=list(levels(comporta$comp),levels(comporta$comp),levels(comporta$ind)))
#Creating the observed transitions matrix.
for(k in 1:length(levels(comporta$ind)))
{
#Creating different tables to each pair to avoid transitions between behaviours of different
pairs.
indi=subset(comporta,subset = comporta$ind==levels(comporta$ind)[k])
# Finding out the position of the “j behaviour”.
for (j in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
{
pos=which(indi$comp==levels(comporta$comp)[j])
# Counting the number of eventer where the “j behaviour” change to “i behaviour” in the
pos+1
for(i in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
{
soma.freq=sum((indi$comp[pos+1]==levels(comporta$comp)[i]),na.rm=TRUE)
#Saving the counting in the empty array.
freq.bruta[j,i,k]=soma.freq
}
}
}
#Summation of the transition observed among pairs
sum.freq=apply(freq.bruta, c(1,2),sum)
#Creating a matrix of proportions of observed transition and adding names to the
behaviours according the names in input
prop=round(sum.freq/apply(sum.freq,1,sum),2)
row.names(prop)=levels(comporta$comp)
colnames(prop)=levels(comporta$comp)
#Creating null scenarios to compare with the observed transitions

```

#Creating an empty array to save the transition matrix

```
s.freq.bruta=array(NA,dim=c(length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$ind))))
```

#Creating an empty array to save the summation of transition matrix

```
c.nulo=array(NA,dim=c(length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$comp)),n.sim))
```

Simulating nsim scenarios with random behaviours sequences using the same behaviours observed by pair.

```
for(o in 1:n.sim)
```

```
{
```

```
  for(l in 1:length(levels(comporta$ind)))
```

```
  {
```

#Creating different tables to each pair to avoid transitions between behaviours of different pairs.

```
s.indi=subset(comporta,subset = comporta$ind==levels(comporta$ind)[l])
```

#Messing up the sequence behaviours.

```
  bagunca=sample(s.indi$comp)
```

```
  for (m in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
```

```
  {
```

Finding out the position of the “m behaviour”.

```
    s.pos=which(bagunca==levels(comporta$comp)[m])
```

```
    for(n in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
```

```
    {
```

Counting the number of eventer where the “m behaviour” change to “n behaviour” in the pos+1

```
      s.soma.freq=sum((bagunca[s.pos+1]==levels(comporta$comp)[n]),na.rm=TRUE)
```

#Saving the counting in the empty array.

```
      s.freq.bruta[m,n,l]=s.soma.freq
```

```
    }  
  }  
}
```

#Summation of the random transition among pairs.

```
soma= apply(s.freq.bruta, c(1,2), sum)
```

#Creating a matrix of proportions of random transition

```
prop.nulo=soma/apply(soma,1,sum)
```

#Saving the proportion in a empty array

```
c.nulo[,o]=prop.nulo
```

```
}
```

#Finding out the proportion of random scenarios where values of random transitions were equal or higher than the observed.

#Creating a empty array to save True-False matrix.

```
dif.cnulo=array(NA,dim=c(length(levels(comporta$comp)),length(levels(comporta$comp)),n.sim))
```

```
  for (r in 1:n.sim)
```

```
{
```

```
  for(q in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
```

```
{
```

```
  for(p in 1:length(levels(comporta$comp)))
```

```
{
```

#Finding out the number of events were the random transitions were equal or higher than the observed transitions

```
diferencas=c.nulo[p,q,r]>=prop[p,q]
```

#Saving results in an empty array

```
dif.cnulo[p,q,r]=diferencas
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

#Calculating the proportion of random transitions equal or higher than the observed in the nsim null scenarios

```
probabilidade= round(apply(dif.cnulo, c(1,2), sum)/n.sim,4)
```

#Adding names to the behaviours according to the input behaviours

```
row.names(probabilidade)=levels(comporta$comp)
```

```
colnames(probabilidade)=levels(comporta$comp)
```

#Creating the output if ind.matrix=TRUE

```
if(ind.matrix==TRUE)
```

```
{return(list(Proporções.observadas=prop,Probabilidade.por.transição=probabilidade,Eventos.por.in  
divíduo=freq.bruta))}
```

#Creating the output if ind.matrix=FALSE

```
else {return(list(Proporções.observadas=prop,Probabilidade.por.transição=probabilidade))}
```

```
}
```

Table S1.

Description of infrequent behavioural units (i.e., behaviours observed in less than 3 couples or with less than two events per couple) or not related to courtship (e.g., grooming behaviours) performed during the courtship by both males (*m*) and females (*f*) of *Oecobius concinnus*. We report the number of pairs for which the behavioural units were recorded, the total number of events and the moment where the events were performed (*After* = after the first mating, *Before* = before the first mating, *Both* = before and after the first mating).

Behaviour	Couples	Events	Moment	Description
Abdominal lateral movement (f)	1	3	After	The female stood still, with the legs extended slightly laterally, moved its abdomen laterally; no perceptible movements of the legs were seen during its performance.
Abdominal lateral movement-Contractions-Legs tapping (m)	1	1	After	The male produced simultaneously "abdominal lateral movement", "contractions", and "legs tapping".
Abdominal lateral movement- Pedipalps movements (m)	3	3	After	The male produced simultaneously "abdomen-lateral movement" and "pedipalps tapping".
Abdominal tapping- Pedipalps movements- Contractions (m)	1	1	After	The male produced simultaneously the "abdominal tapping", "pedipalps tapping", and "contractions".
Approaches- Pedipalps movements (m)	1	1	After	The male produced simultaneously "approaches" and "pedipalps tapping".
Contractions- Leg grooming (m)	1	1	After	The male produced simultaneously "contractions" and "leg grooming".
Leg grooming (m)	4	26	Both	The male approached any leg to his mouth, beginning at the proximal portion of the metatarsus and then moving distally.
Legs tapping- Abdominal lateral movement- Pedipalps movements (m)	1	1	After	The male produced simultaneously "abdominal lateral movement", "legs tapping", and "pedipalps tapping".
Legs tapping- Pedipalps movements (m)	4	4	After	The male produced simultaneously "legs tapping" and "pedipalps tapping".
Spinnerets brushing (m, f)	1(f) 2(m)	1(f) 3(m)	Both	Spiders twisted the abdomen laterally, exposing its ventral zone and combing the spinnerets with rapid movements of tarsi I, II, or III.
Lines placement (m)	2	2	Before	Male placed silk lines on the female tent web.